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ADPI
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MUNDARIJA

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4. Pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining mediakompetentligini rivojlantirish muammosining holati o'rganilgan. Dunyo xorij olimlarning tajribasi va fikr mulohazalari asosida nazariy metodolik yondashuv aniqlanib o'rganilgan. "Informatika va axborot texnologiyalari" kursini o'qitish jarayonida axborot texnologiyalari, multimedia-texnologiyalar vositasida rivojlantirish. Multimedia asoslariga oid, mediakompetentlik darajasini oshirishga qaratilgan maxsus kurslarni, pedagogik faoliyatda ham mediakompetentlikning yuqori darajasini namoyon qilish imkonini beradi.

Yuqoridagilardan kelib chiqib, bo'lajak o'qituvchilarning pedagogika oliy ta'lim muassasalari talabalarining mediakompetentlikning rivojlantirish mazmuni takomillashtirish, mediakompetentligini rivojlantirish metodikasini ishlab chiqish zaruriyati aniqlandi.

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METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT LEARNING BASED ON INNOVATIVE APPROACHES (CASE STUDY OF VISUAL ARTS AND ENGINEERING GRAPHICS EDUCATION)

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Annotatsiya. *Mazkur tadqiqotda talabalarining mustaqil o'rganishini rivojlantirishda innovatsion yondashuvlarning muhimligi, xususan, tasviriy san'at va muhandislik grafikasi fanlarida ta'lim jarayonida yangi pedagogik usullarni qo'llash zarurligi o'rganilgan. Talabalarining bilim, ko'nikma*

va kompetensiyalarini oshirish uchun mustaqil o'qitishning ahamiyati, shuningdek, turli ta'lim metodlarining qo'llanilishi ta'kidlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsion yondashuvlar, mustaqil o'rganish, tasviriy san'at, muhandislik grafikasi, pedagogik metodlar.

Аннотация. В данном исследовании подчеркивается важность инновационных подходов в развитии самостоятельного обучения студентов, особенно в дисциплинах изобразительного искусства и инженерной графики. Рассматривается необходимость применения новых педагогических методов для повышения знаний, навыков и компетенций студентов.

Ключевые слова: инновационные подходы, самостоятельное обучение, изобразительное искусство, инженерная графика, педагогические методы.

Abstract. This study highlights the importance of innovative approaches in developing students' independent learning, particularly in visual arts and engineering graphics. It also emphasizes the benefits of this approach, such as empowering students to take control of their learning and fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter, which should motivate them to embrace this method.

Key words: innovative approaches, independent learning, visual arts, engineering graphics, pedagogical methods.

In the current educational landscape, there is a global trend towards early education, particularly in the arts and visual arts. This study is particularly relevant as it explores the potential of innovative approaches in the context of a proposed return to an eleven-year general education system in our country. The system will offer 64 different trades, tailored to the characteristics of the district and community, and will prioritize the establishment of educational centres, unique art schools, specialized schools, and higher education institutions for the artistic and aesthetic education of the youth.

On December 20, 2022, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, delivered a pivotal address to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan. In this address, he underscored the crucial role of education in developing the New Uzbekistan, stating, 'Improving the quality of education is the only correct path to the development of the New Uzbekistan. As our ancestor, Yusuf Khasm Hajib said: 'Where there is intelligence, there will be greatness; where there is knowledge, there will be superiority.' This underscores the necessity of continuing the reforms we have initiated, fostering more frequent visits to educational institutions, engaging in more discussions with teachers and mentors, and collectively addressing the issues they raise to enhance the quality of educational and training activities.'

This continuous focus includes our prospective plans to build a great future for the new Uzbekistan. At the same time, the current era demands to enhance students' knowledge, skills, and competencies using innovative methodological approaches during the teaching process. It is becoming necessary for students to participate more in the independent learning process to understand their professional activities better and to model the assigned tasks appropriately. As educators and policymakers, we must implement these changes and empower our students for their future.

Student independence in the educational process is a cornerstone, leading to the development of independent study, research, and creative direction skills and competencies in students. This independence is manifested in various activities, including the search for educational information, the analytical perception and reprocessing of this information, its practical reinforcement, the summarization of knowledge, and the application of acquired skills to solve educational and creative practical problems [1]

Students often face creative challenges and fear the blank page. Therefore, tasks that include regulatory functions (reducing fatigue, relieving stress), cognitive (more active use of imagination, developing various aspects of personality), and developmental (self-regulation of emotions, personal growth) components are necessary. Mastering various graphic styles helps develop the artistic abilities of students and future visual arts teachers. To be successful in the visual arts teaching profession, a student must be able to:

- Create conditions for teaching and implementing educational programs using innovative methods and pedagogical technologies that enhance the opportunities of the educational environment;
- Master the process of conducting diagnostics to assess the quality of the educational process;
- Implement the educational process taking into account the specific features of working with talented children in the chosen activity;
- Develop additional professional training programs to assist in students' development.

In this context, the necessity of teaching the techniques and methods of graphic arts to students of the art studies direction is undeniable.

Currently, several studies in theoretical pedagogy are being conducted on this topic. For instance, O.Yu. Polyanichko in his work proposes a model of the system of independent classroom and extracurricular drawing activities from the perspective of a competency-based approach. According to the researcher, education for students needs to be transformed into a personally significant activity [2].

E.N. Trushchenko in her scientific work defines the competency-based approach that motivates professional activity as follows:

- Developing a motivational and value-based attitude towards students' independent drawing work;
- Creating educational materials that facilitate the gradual transition from educational activity to professional activity;
- Using additional methodological materials (programs, score-rating cards, assessment tools repository) is suggested [3].

O.E. Lebedev presented the main aspects of the competency-based approach:

- The main goal of education is to form the ability to solve educational and creative problems independently;
- The substantive directions of education define methodological, didactic, and also social experiences in solving problems of various levels; organizing the educational process includes adherence to psychological, pedagogical, and educational requirements;
- Students' results are assessed based on the level of education achieved at a certain stage of education [4].

N.V. Bordovskaya believes that the increase in extracurricular activities does not yield the expected results for the following reasons:

- The substantive directions of methodological developments are not related to the goals of forming and developing specific knowledge, skills, and competencies;
- A large volume of tasks is performed formally by students;
- Methodological developments for independent work do not ensure the quality performance of the task [5].

The theoretical aspects of organising independent work have shown only some researchers' opinions. The problem has been partially solved and demands further substantive and methodological development, particularly the development of non-traditional exercises with a reflective effect.

The object of research - The methodology for developing independent learning of students based on an innovative approach (a case study of visual arts and engineering graphics education).

The subject of research - The content and methods of organizing independent work in the "Drawing".

Visual arts as a school subject, like other subjects in general education schools, serves to educate students and shape them into well-rounded individuals comprehensively. Visual arts express a person's inner emotional experiences, thoughts, moods, and the beauty of nature through various colors and forms. By leveraging the impactful force of their lessons, teachers can enhance students' spiritual, moral, and artistic culture using various methods, forms, and tools. Today, the interest in applying new pedagogical and information technologies, interactive methods, and innovative classes in the educational process is growing. One of the main reasons for this necessity is that, whereas traditional education has only taught students to acquire prepared knowledge, modern technologies teach them to find, independently study, analyze, and even draw their own conclusions about the knowledge they acquire. Nowadays, teachers' ability to move from proficiency to creativity in teaching using modern methods is required for the development of the education sector. Using non-traditional methods to conduct classes helps identify talented students, creates an environment of confidence for underachieving students, and fosters friendship, mutual compassion, and consensus among students in the classroom. When using new pedagogical technologies and interactive methods, teachers must first thoroughly familiarise themselves with the purpose, content, application methods, and conditions of these technologies and then apply them fully, partially, or in certain aspects to their subjects based on the methodological characteristics of their field. Non-traditional methods of teaching positively affect the quality and effectiveness of classes.

In this context, methods such as differentiation, group work, discussions, debates, data banks, "Brainstorming," "Cluster-Network," "Sunflower," "Boomerang," "Muzyorar, and presentations are effective according to the principles of attracting attention, preventing boredom, promoting teamwork, encouraging class participation, comparing one's own ideas with others, and fostering genuine debate. In visual arts classes, interactive methods can be used in tests, organizational parts, homework assignments, consolidating new topics, revising, and identifying students' BKM achievements.

Brainstorming Method. The term "Brainstorming" is derived from the English word "Brainstorm," where "Brain" means brain and "Storm" denotes storm or excitement. This method's literal translation as "Brain Excitement" reveals its true essence, but it is more aptly called "Brainstorming." This technique can be used in visual arts classes. For example, recently covered and long-covered topics are presented in the form of quick questions, and through short answers, students' memories are reinforced, and the knowledge and skills acquired in the class are consolidated. This cultivates students' quick-thinking and responsive traits.

Presentation Method. In presentations, each student's work is evaluated through its display. The teacher creates conditions and provides significant support for participants to present their achievements, knowledge, and accomplishments. Through presenting their work, students learn from their mistakes and develop qualities such as self-management.

The success of presentations, the renewal of ideas and thoughts, and the development of free-thinking are determined based on the audience's conclusions, allowing students to recognize their own achievements and shortcomings. The organization of students' creative "Exhibitions" in quarterly control works demonstrates the importance of this method because it is convenient and favourable to identify the innovative, practical, and theoretical knowledge, skills, and competencies that students have acquired over the quarter through the "Presentation" method.

"Networks" or "Cluster" Method. The branching of thoughts is a pedagogical strategy that helps students deeply study a topic, teaching them to branch related concepts or specific ideas organically and sequentially about the topic. The branching is organized as follows:

- Any idea related to the topic is expressed in one word and written down sequentially.
- The process of expressing ideas continues.
- During the class, efforts are made to increase the interconnectivity and sequence of ideas.
- Once the ideas and suggestions are written down, the teacher uses the writings to reveal the true essence and content of the discussed problem or topic.

Domestic researchers of the theory of pedagogy, such as S.I. Arkhangelsky, R.A. Nizamov, I.I. Ilyasov, and A.G. Molibog, have worked on the organization and development of students' independent work structure. These researchers consider the term 'independent work' as an organised, teacher-led active activity of students to achieve set goals and objectives within a specified time frame" [5]. "The conducted analysis of the theoretical aspects of organizing independent work showed only some opinions of researchers. In our view, the problem under consideration is only partially resolved and requires further in-depth development. Based on this, we conclude that there is a need to create a set of educational and methodological materials on drawing for students, the content of which should be directed towards the motivational aspect (using various teaching methods, including active ones; a variety of tasks and materials) for better mastery of educational material, as well as successful and high-quality results within the studied discipline" [6].

The set of educational and methodological materials includes:

- A program that reflects classical drawing tasks as well as preparatory exercises;
- A visual development with a step-by-step development of a complex thematic still life;
- A model of a methodological system, including goals, objectives, means, forms, teaching methods, and assessment criteria.

"In the training of art teachers, drawing objects from reality is the fundamental type of specialized activity. The 'Drawing' discipline is implemented through classroom work and independent work. The independent activity of students in the 'Drawing' discipline includes searching for educational information, its analytical perception, practical consolidation, generalization, and the use of acquired knowledge and skills to solve educational and creative practical tasks" [6]. A significant role in organizing this process is assigned to the methodological activities of the teacher in developing and structuring the content of independent work" [7]. "The independent work of students in drawing includes both the

study of theoretical aspects of drawing and the practical execution of tasks" [8]. "To make the independence of students' work more effective, it is necessary to fulfill some conditions:

- Structure the educational material according to tasks and select the form of its implementation. The teacher needs to change didactic tasks, execution materials, teaching methods to maintain students' attention [9].

- A positive effect is also possible with an unconventional form of independent work (conducting a master class);

- Develop a set of educational and methodological materials and recommendations for their use for the theoretical study and practical execution of independent tasks, which have a system-forming significance in the process of forming and developing professional competencies;

- Organize forms of control over the progress of independent work.

In the framework of independent work, self-control is primarily acceptable. However, it manifests at the final stages of forming the skill of independent work in drawing, since most students do not have a specialized education and, therefore, need control over both classroom and independent work (individual, frontal, group)" [10]. "To achieve a high level of extracurricular independent work of students, certain requirements must be provided, namely: to develop methods for organizing extracurricular work of students. The methods can be quite diverse (positive changes occur in the choice of teaching methods in the following sequence: from the predominance of the explanatory-illustrative and reproductive methods at the beginning of training to the method of problem presentation at the final stages)" [11].

The explanatory-illustrative method. The specifics of students' activities in the learning process through this method consist in the perception of knowledge, its comprehension, and memorization. Examples of using the explanatory-illustrative method: viewing and analyzing paintings, films, reading. The method is also used in recognizing observation, which includes forming ideas about the properties and qualities of objects and phenomena (structure, form, tone), etc." [12]. "The reproductive method. The specifics of students' activities: reproducing knowledge and ways of actions based on samples, memorization. For example, copying a graphic sheet by an artist with specified techniques and methods of execution [13].

The method of problem presentation: the teacher's activity consists of formulating the problem and showing how to solve it. The problem situation should be accessible to students, not solvable with already available knowledge, and should contain contradictions. The specifics of students' activities: perception and comprehension of knowledge, mental forecasting of ways to solve, memorization. Example of an assignment: depicting a household item and applying hatching lines according to the form. The task: to grasp the characteristics of lines depending on the form of the object, develop the ability to analyze; straight lines studied will not give volume to a round object, for instance. The problem is solved during a heuristic conversation: analyzing the form of the depicted object and the nature of hatching lines, students conclude the need for their correspondence [14].

The partial search method. The teacher's task is to set the problem, present assignments for performing individual stages of problem-solving, plan the sequential path of solution, and guide students' activities. Students' activity involves perceiving and comprehending the assignment, independently performing individual steps. Example: exercises on transferring the mastered method of action to new content. Practical assignment: performing a tonal layout. The task is teaching tonal vision and consolidating covered topics.

The research method aims to develop creative activity, mastering ways to solve problems. Examples of application: creative exercises and experimentation. Practical assignment: illustration of classical literary works through hatching. Tasks: developing and consolidating hatching skills and independently creating an expressive image. It is necessary to develop special educational and methodological materials on the studied topics (articles, pedagogical drawings, diagram-drawings, educational aids).

"When compiling methodological developments for the independent work of students in the 'Drawing' discipline, it is necessary to take into account various indicators of the level of development of artistic skills (technical skills, the ability to translate a real object into a graphic image)". "Students are tasked with:

- Studying the content of theoretical works and developments of well-known figures of art pedagogy, which justify and have historically tested graphic means of form formation, construction of forms in space, and means of graphic expressiveness;

- Using the acquired knowledge to achieve the necessary level of understanding and readiness to freely use various graphic means of expression in educational and creative works;

- Contributing to the development of professional, communicative, and executive skills and abilities (the ability to clearly convey educational material, theoretical and practical mastery of teaching methods, execution of images with various materials)".

"In solving these tasks, one can talk about the professional readiness of the student to solve the set tasks. These components have a positive impact on the quality of the work performed and the assimilation of material in the process of learning to draw. The criteria for evaluating the work performed by the student are assessed depending on:

- Timely completion of the educational task;
- The degree of resolution of the composition, scale of the image;
- Observance of the proportions of objects;
- Correct construction of the structures of objects;
- Competent tonal solution".

"Control over the performance of independent work in the process of learning to draw for students should be carried out by the teacher only in the classroom". "Students need independent work, which constitutes one of the forms of the educational process, contributing to the formation of the ability to navigate the information space and self-education independently" [15].

Conclusion. The research highlights the essential role of innovative methodologies in developing students' independent learning, particularly in visual arts and engineering graphics. The study underscores the necessity of integrating new pedagogical approaches to foster students' skills, knowledge, and competencies.

Key findings indicate that:

- **Student Independence:** Independent learning is crucial for students to develop research, creativity, and problem-solving skills. This involves searching for educational information, analyzing and reprocessing it, and applying the acquired knowledge to practical and creative tasks.

- **Innovative Approaches:** Methods such as brainstorming, presentations, and clustering significantly enhance the learning process by making it more interactive and engaging. These methods help students develop quick-thinking, self-management, and free-thinking skills.

- **Pedagogical Techniques:** The study emphasizes the importance of using various teaching methods, including explanatory-illustrative, reproductive, problem presentation, and research methods, to cater to different learning stages and needs.

- **Teacher's Role:** Teachers play a pivotal role in organizing and structuring independent work, ensuring that the educational material is aligned with the students' goals and tasks. This includes creating educational and methodological materials and providing the necessary support and control.

- **Educational Environment:** A conducive educational environment that leverages modern technologies and non-traditional teaching methods can significantly improve the quality and effectiveness of education. This environment helps identify talented students, supports underachieving students, and fosters a collaborative and supportive classroom culture.

Overall, the study concludes that innovative methodological approaches are vital for enhancing the quality of education in visual arts and engineering graphics. By focusing on student independence, interactive methods, and teacher support, educators can better prepare students for their professional activities and future careers.

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